

Article

Cause–Effect Modelling of Soil Liming in Poland

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Abstract: This research aimed to use the cause-and-effect diagram (model) as a method to describe the 15 main factors (for example, awareness, knowledge and motivation of farmers, farmers income, institutional and financial support, condition of the natural environment, healthiness of the population, etc.) leading to soil acidification, their impact on soil health and ecosystem functions, and how soil liming serves as a remedial measure. The cause-and-effect model was developed based on questionnaire studies as a part of the project ‘Opportunities and Barriers to the Use of Soil Liming for Improving the Economic Efficiency of Agricultural Production and Reducing Eutrophication of Surface Waters’ in 2022–2023. The results showed that the effects of soil acidification and liming as well as their interrelationships are multifaceted and affect agricultural production economics, agricultural land and crop prices, environmental health and biodiversity, as well as soil productivity and food security. The causes of this situation can be attributed to social, technological–logistical–technical, and economic factors. To change the existing situation, it is necessary to take effective steps to motivate farmers to lime their soils. The most effective would be (1) offering training courses for farmers to discuss the benefits that a farmer can achieve by maintaining optimum soil pH levels while growing a specific crop species; (2) implementing liming payment programs that will be more attractive and motivating from the farmers’ perspective; and (3) linking agri-environmental payments to the necessity of systematic testing of soil pH levels and maintaining optimal pH levels under specific crops species.

Keywords: soil pH; soil liming; soil health; sustainable development; cause-and-effect diagram; economic efficiency

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1. Introduction

An estimated 60–70% of the soil in the European Union is considered unhealthy, with 2.8 million areas identified as potentially polluted due to insufficient soil protection measures. In addition, an unspecified proportion of soils has also been deemed unhealthy as a result of indirect impacts from air pollution and climate change. The European Green Deal

(EGD³) aims to address the escalating global climate crisis and the associated environmental degradation [1,2]. Relevant areas of the EGD³ directly related to the agricultural sector and rural areas include the creation of a fair, healthy, and environmentally friendly food system (farm to fork strategy) [3]; the protection of soil; as well as the protection and restoration of ecosystems and biodiversity (soil strategy) [4].

The European farm-to-fork strategy is designed to change the food sector to reach a palpable reduction in its environmental and climate footprint. The ambitious targets set by the European Commission are expected to be implemented by 2030, including a 50% reduction in the use of pesticides, 20% reduction in the use of artificial fertilisers, and a 25% increase in the share of organic farming [3]. The intended reduction in the use of artificial fertilisers and plant protection agents is expected to produce a major decrease in the load of nutrients leaching into groundwater and surface water, reduce soil acidification, and increase biodiversity in rural areas [5–7].

The acidification of agricultural soil is a very serious problem also observed in Poland [8,9]. Low soil pH has an adverse effect on the quantity and quality of yield, especially in the case of pH-sensitive crops [10–12]. This impacts the economic efficiency of farm operations [13,14]. Acidification affects more than 30% of soil worldwide and more than 70% of soil in Poland [15,16]. There are both natural and anthropogenic reasons for the acidification of soil [17–19].

Natural factors behind acidification of soil are mainly related to pedogenesis and climatic conditions [20]. For example, soil pH depends on the parent rock from which the soil is formed. It determines the chemical and physical properties that translate into the fertility and quality of soil [21]. Globally, a significant area of agricultural soil lacks carbonates and has acidic pH [16,22–24]. Nearly 40% of the world's arable land is highly acidic [9]. In Poland, non-carbonate, light and very light soils prevail, and their acidic pH is not optimal for the majority of crops [25].

Natural factors that cause soil acidification also include chemical precipitation, which leads to the loss of calcium and magnesium cations from the soil, thus reducing its pH. The process is even more intensive in the case of acid rain caused by industrial activity [26]. Precipitation washes out cations (Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , K^+ , and Na^+) from soil, which leads to decalcification and acidification of the topsoil used for agriculture. The loss of CaO per ha of agricultural land is estimated at 350–450 $\text{kg}\cdot\text{ha}^{-1}$ per year [27]. The loss should be compensated by adding fertilisers that can deacidify the soil. They should also optimise soil pH, adjusting it to the needs of a specific crop [16,27].

Moreover, mineral fertilisers, pesticides, and other chemicals also have a big impact on the acidity of agricultural soil. These substances can alter soil pH depending on their molecular structure and physico-chemical properties [28]. Pesticides with low pH and sulphur content may lead to soil acidification [29]. The process is also often stimulated by the conversion of nitrates to acidic chemicals [30]. Ammonium compounds can also undergo bacterial transformation [31], leading to the release of hydrogen ions and thus increasing acidification. However, it should be noted that the effect of nitrogen fertilisers on soil pH varies and depends on the distribution of rainfall and temperatures, the type and primary pH of soil, as well as the application method, rates, and type of fertiliser application.

An important environmental consequence of agricultural soil acidification is the reduced biodiversity due to the extinction of the most sensitive stenotopic species of plants, animals, fungi, and micro-organisms [32]. Long-term changes in soil pH lead to changes in the composition of a biotic community. This is particularly important in the case of microorganisms since they play an important role in the decomposition of pesticides in soil. The acidification of soil can reduce the enzymatic activity of microorganisms, which may lead to a reduced ability to decompose chemical compounds [33].

Negative effects of lowered soil pH include an increased risk of erosion. Acidic soils are more susceptible to erosion due to their physical and chemical properties as well as the composition of the vegetation layer [34].

The acidification of soil can stimulate the movement of chemical substances through surface runoff and watercourses. Acidic soil can also increase greenhouse gas emissions, including carbon dioxide and methane [35]. This may occur due to increased activity of certain microorganisms involved in the decomposition of organic matter and bound carbon release. Moreover, acidic soil can also significantly reduce plant productivity [36]. Soil liming is an important agrotechnical treatment that effectively increases soil pH. According to [37], there is a strong spatial differentiation of crop production and its intensity in Poland depending chiefly on the quality of soil. The level of deacidifying fertilisation is also varied but significantly too low. According to [37,38], the level of soil liming in agricultural production ranged from about 51 kg·ha⁻¹ of agricultural land (UAA) in the Świętokrzyskie and Małopolskie Voivodships to nearly 146.5 kg·ha⁻¹ of UAA in the Opolskie Voivodship. Even in the Opolskie Voivodship, which performed best in this respect, the average level of lime fertilisation was three times too low in relation to optimal level (Table 1).

Table 1. Lime fertilisers consumption (per pure component) per ha in Polish agricultural land in 2020 [38].

Voivodships of Poland	Lime Fertilisers
	kg·ha ⁻¹ of UAA
Dolnośląskie	139.9
Kujawsko-Pomorskie	111.0
Lubelskie	85.5
Lubuskie	69.6
Łódzkie	96.5
Małopolskie	52.4
Mazowieckie	71.6
Opolskie	146.6
Podkarpackie	71.3
Podlaskie	67.7
Pomorskie	100.9
Śląskie	80.9
Świętokrzyskie	50.9
Warmińsko-Mazurskie	89.9
Wielkopolskie	96.3
Zachodniopomorskie	114.4

The analysis of fertilisation-related data from the 2010 and 2020 National Agricultural Census [38] shows that the volume of lime fertilisers used by farmers in Poland is several times below the optimal level. The Institute of Soil Science and Plant Cultivation—State Research Institute in Puławy (IUNG—PIB) estimates that the demand of Polish agriculture for soil liming is about 31 million t CaO, i.e., about 2 t CaO per ha⁻¹ of UAA on average [16].

To identify factors and barriers affecting low levels of soil liming on agricultural land in Poland in 2021–2022, surveys were conducted among farmers and employees of agricultural institutions as a part of the project ‘Opportunities and Barriers to the Use of Soil Liming for Improving the Economic Efficiency of Agricultural Production and Reducing Eutrophication of Surface Waters’.

The main goals of the project focused on answering the following questions:

1. What is the current level of knowledge among the farmers and employees of agricultural institutions about the effects of soil liming?
2. What soil-liming support programmes are well known by farmers and employees of agricultural institutions?
3. What factors prevent farmers from sufficiently using the soil-liming support programmes?
4. How will the future of farms be affected by the implementation of the European Green Deal (EDG³) concept?

The surveys were conducted in Poland in four voivodeships: Podkarpackie, Małopolskie, Opolskie, and Zachodniopomorskie, which differ in soil quality, farmland size, and social and cultural conditions. Two districts (from each voivodeship) with low and high levels of lime fertiliser application were selected for the study. The analysis of the results was based on 443 questionnaires filled out by farmers (35 questions, including 3 advanced table questions and 9 providing for the possibility of more than one answer) and 325 by employees of agricultural institutions (22 questions, including 1 advanced table question and 5 providing for the possibility of more than one answer). Pivot tables were used to verify the completed questionnaires, which allowed the identification of missing data (blank fields) and detection of errors in the questionnaires [39].

The questionnaire studies showed that the occurrence of individual barriers limiting soil liming depended on many features of the farms and the user. These barriers were more common on smaller, economically weaker farms, where agricultural production was an additional rather than the main source of income. The three groups of factors limiting soil liming were identified (Table 2):

- Economic;
- Logistical and technological;
- Social.

Table 2. The main factors limiting the use of lime fertilisers indicated by respondents (synthesised results based on [39]).

The Main Factors Limiting the Use of Lime Fertilisers in Poland	Number of Responses Provided by Farmers (n = 433)	Number of Responses Provided by Employees of Agricultural Institutions (n = 325)
Economic:		
- Limited financial resources of farms	260	219
Logistical and technical:		
- Lack of equipment for applying the lime fertiliser	140	133
Social:		
- Lack of knowledge of correct agricultural fertilisation techniques in agricultural crops	53	65

Based on the surveys, it was found that the main factor limiting soil liming is an economic factor—the lack of financial resources for the purchase of lime fertiliser. A significant number of respondents also indicated a lack of equipment for applying lime fertiliser. The lack of knowledge and training in this field as well as the same for the next generations was also a major limitation of soil liming, according to respondents (Table 2).

It should also be noted that nearly half of the 433 farmers did not attend any meeting, training, or course on soil-liming techniques or support programmes, and nearly one-fifth of the respondents did not remember such information being given to them from any agricultural institutions (Figure 1).

Therefore, the aim of the research was to use the questionnaire studies to develop a cause-and-effect diagram to highlight the interactions between the reduction in soil acidity and soil liming, taking into account the economic, technological, as well as social aspects.

Figure 1. Number of responses provided by farmers regarding participants in training (courses) on soil liming (n = 433); results based on [39].

2. Materials and Methods

As part of the objective set in this paper, typical systems thinking tools were reviewed. As evidenced in the works of the precursor of systems thinking [40,41], these include causality loop diagrams, system archetypes, mathematical models, social studies, and computer simulations of systems. Undoubtedly, the operation of some archetypes could be found in the relationships between the natural, technological, economic, and social aspects of soil acidification. However, it was recognised that these elementary relationship structures could be subject of separate research. Moreover, mathematical models and computer simulations of the systems would require extremely labour-intensive mathematical operations on the existing knowledge about the systems and relationships between the natural, technological, economic, and social aspects of agricultural production. This knowledge would have to be transformed into mathematical equations, and if computer simulations were to be the outcome, we would additionally need to calibrate all the data streams and initial states of all the resources in the system. In this context, causal loop diagrams and social research were the most promising and complementary.

The practical use of cause–effect diagrams as tools of the systems approach is well known in the literature [40–46]. Their undoubted benefit is that they represent relationships that are difficult to describe verbally since normal language shows interrelationships in linear causal chains, whereas system diagrams show that loops, i.e., circular causal chains, exist in the actual system.

As noted by many researchers studying systems [40–43], causality loop diagrams, also known as cause–effect diagrams, are often the first step in developing a system model. This, in turn, enables its subsequent simulation [44–46]. The systems are more than a simple sum of their elements, and the interrelationships between these elements play a crucial role in understanding them [42]. This is supported by causal diagrams, with their four key elements:

- Arrow (\rightarrow)—an element generally indicating a cause-and-effect relationship;
- Double strikethrough (\parallel)—an element indicating that the effect is delayed;
- Plus (+)—an element indicating that variables connected by an arrow change in the same direction (increase in cause translates into increase in effect);
- Minus (−)—an element indicating that variables connected by an arrow change in the opposite direction (increase in cause translates into decrease in effect).

The correct interpretation of pluses and minuses is very important for system diagrams. It is important to remember that these signs cannot be taken literally and do not indicate (respectively) an increase or decrease in the value of a variable. They characterise the relationship between the elements of the system, i.e., a change in cause and effect. This can take place in the same direction (+) or in the opposite direction (−). Thus, the value of the variable reached by the minus arrow can both increase and decrease, depending on the direction of change of the cause [42].

The systems theory was used to develop a cause–effect diagram in the Vensim PLE 8.0.1 programme by Ventana based on the socio-economic research that identified 15 key aspects of soil acidification and soil liming and their interrelationships (Figure 2). The Vensim program is useful because it allows not only the development of simulation mathematical models but also conceptual models, namely cause–effect models. A cause–effect diagram presents the structure of a system and is used to describe the relationships between its elements. Such a model is a starting point for considering how changes in one element of the system will affect other elements; hence, it is common practice to place signs (+ or −) at the heads of relationship arrows in Vensim.

Figure 2. Cause-and-effect model of soil liming, generated in the Vensim programme. Source: own study.

In developing such a model, both exogenous variables (e.g., institutional support or training to increase farmers' awareness and knowledge) and endogenous variables, which are the result of interactions in the model (e.g., the action of the sorption complex, pesticide use, or the state of surface water quality), can be used. Although the causal model is not a mathematical model and does not allow simulation of the system, its

cognitive value is also valuable. Such a model organises knowledge within a given domain, facilitating the identification of key elements of the system and their interactions. In the case of the presented issue, it can serve as a starting point for discussing the need for soil deacidification policies and their long-term effects. The cause–effect diagram presented in this work was developed as a synthesis of the knowledge gained during the project. It resulted from literature studies, analysis of the results of the surveys conducted among farmers and experts, numerous discussions and in-depth interviews, as well as discussions within the project team (representatives of different scientific disciplines), thus providing different perspectives on the phenomenon of soil acidification. The cause–effect diagram does not contain equations. It was gradually expanded starting with the two key elements of soil acidification and soil liming, and it was subjected to critical evaluation by the project team. The presented diagram is a specific exemplification of the social research carried out into the determinants and barriers of soil liming in Poland.

3. Results and Discussion

The interpretation of the diagram (Figure 2) starts with the fundamental issue of soil acidification, the effects of which can manifest themselves on many levels. However, the strength of their impact escapes precise measurement. Their nature can be described as follows:

- Directly agricultural (production and income), affecting the economics of agricultural production;
- Market-related, affecting prices of agricultural land and crops;
- Economic–environmental, resulting from increased environmental pollution and decline in biodiversity;
- Social and health, affecting the cost of animal welfare and human health;
- Social and administrative, resulting from the social cost of maintaining soil productivity and food security.

In each of these spheres, acidification generates additional costs and loss of economic benefits.

3.1. Environmental Effects

The amount of mineral fertilisers as well as other nutrients supplied to plants should be adjusted to their needs and to the climate and soil conditions, weather patterns, or position. Otherwise, the expenses and labour will not be effective, and a significant portion of them can be wasted [39]. From technological and economic points of view, a prerequisite of optimised mineral fertilisation is to bring the soil to a condition that will promote optimal plant growth. The understanding of the role of soil pH control is crucial in optimising mineral fertilisation.

Soil acidification, limiting the assimilation of macro- and microelements, affects the effectiveness of mineral fertilisation and thus also the yield of plants [11,12]. Indeed, it should be noted that with the increase in assimilation, the efficiency of fertilisation also increases [30]. Farmers can then achieve a similar yield of plants with reduced application of mineral fertilisers. Therefore, crop production costs can decrease, with a positive impact on the returns from the agricultural activity. A reduction in mineral fertiliser application leads to a decrease in the amount of biogenic components reaching surface waters and their eutrophication [39,47].

While determining crop health and therefore resistance to pests, the assimilation of macro- and micronutrients reduces the need to use pesticides. Although they have a positive effect on crop yields, they diminish crop quality. At the same time, pesticides destroy not only organisms harmful to plants but also those that are beneficial. Pesticides, carried by the wind and washed by rain from the fields, additionally deteriorate the quality of watercourses and water bodies [48]. Their consumption indirectly deteriorates the environment and ultimately leads to the decline in public health. The assimilation of macro and micronutrients is, therefore, an important direct and indirect determinant of

the quality of agricultural products. It can, for example, manifest itself in the reduction in harmful processes, such as the absorption of heavy metal, and in a number of positive phenomena that occur when the plant receives the desired amount of nitrogen, potassium, phosphorus, sulphur, and calcium. As theory and practice indicate, these elements help plants to become more resistant to fungi. This reduces the need to control fungi through the use of pesticides. Moreover, plants develop stronger root systems, which increases the efficiency of photosynthesis [49,50].

The environmental effects of soil acidification include, first and foremost, changes in biodiversity [32]. This is related to the adaptation of plants, animals, fungi, microorganisms, and other organisms that coexist and interact in a given ecosystem to new conditions. Thus, long-term changes in soil pH lead to a complete reconstruction of the biocenosis. Additional effects of the changes in soil pH are the increased threat of erosion, as acidic soils are less stable due to both their different chemical composition and the different composition of the plant cover [34].

Changes in the soil pH can have long-range negative consequences, especially in neighbouring aquatic ecosystems. This is mainly due to the movement of chemicals via surface runoff and watercourses. Acidic soil conditions can also increase the emission of greenhouse gases such as carbon dioxide and methane [35]. This is due to the increased activity of certain microorganisms involved in organic matter decomposition and the release of carbon [36] as well as lower plant productivity in acidic soils.

3.2. Social–Economic Effects

Soil acidification may result from a poor agricultural culture and the improper crop rotation, mishandling of agrotechnical procedures, and insufficient deacidification fertilisation [51–53]. Although mainly related to rural areas and agriculture, the economic and social consequences of soil acidification extend beyond farm operations. The agricultural consequences of soil acidification include an increase in agricultural production cost and a decrease in yield, which affects the income earned by farmers [39]. The abandonment of soil liming drives farmers to search for crop varieties and species with an increased resistance to low soil pH [54,55]. Such species are often characterised by low yield and inferior performance. There are also economic consequences of a decline in the quality of food produced in acidic soil. Poor food and fodder quality adversely affect human and animal health. In this context, to produce healthy food and high-quality fodder, we need to provide optimal conditions for the growth of plants [9,56–59].

Commodity farming aims to optimise agricultural production through a precise application of fertilisers and plant protection agents to develop a sustainable, intelligent, and environmentally friendly food system. The European Green Deal stipulates that farmers applying for direct payments have to meet higher standards of good agricultural practices compatible with environmental protection [3]. This may contribute to a significant decrease in yield and consequently reduced farm income. Optimising soil pH can increase crop yields by several to tens of percentages, depending on the crop [37,38]. In this context, comprehensive changes and an integrated approach to fertiliser and pesticide management practices in EU countries are needed. Such an approach should encourage farmers to reduce pesticide dependence and promote relevant farming methods (crop rotation, control of soil pH through liming, precision farming, etc.).

The importance of maintaining an optimum soil pH for specific plant groups has been frequently addressed in the literature both in Poland and in other European countries [60–69]. Nevertheless, farmers often do not apply deacidification fertilising and do not resort to subsidies for agricultural land liming [38]. In 2019–2023, the support for soil liming and the preservation of soil was implemented in Poland as part of the national support measures for agriculture and rural areas. The priority aid programmes implemented by the National Fund for Environmental Protection and Water Management aimed at supporting environmental protection projects. The programmes were defined in the 2014 Strategy for Energy Security and Environment [70]. The strategy included the programme ‘Rational

Waste Management and Protection of the Earth's Surface'. It listed ten key tasks, one of which was environmental regeneration of soil through liming. It had the form of the 'National programme for environmental regeneration of soil through liming', aimed to provide financial support for the regeneration of soil acidified as a result of anthropogenic activity [71].

The economic and social effects of soil acidification, which are taken into account by the developed cause–effect model of soil liming, have been very rarely described in the literature (Figure 2). This makes it difficult to analyse the interrelationships between soil acidification and soil liming.

As the results presented on the graph (Figure 2) point out, soil acidification is a multifaceted phenomenon that can affect the supply side of the market, including a decline in the quality and availability of local food, the increased role of imports, and a general increase in the price of food products [72–75]. The lower soil culture, the reduced biological fitness, and the poor suitability for agricultural production can downgrade the market value of land, especially when agricultural production is the only potential designation of land. According to research, as the quality of agricultural land deteriorates, the price per hectare in private trade decreases as well [76–82].

Soil acidification can also disrupt supply chains due to the reduction in or the lack of certain plant species and varieties. This may render animal husbandry difficult or impossible. Yet another consequence of the process is the reduction in the number of jobs in the agricultural sector and related sectors in a given region. A reduced production scale and deteriorated quality of agricultural produce diminish the raw material base. As noted by [83], impoverished flora and fauna or unfavourable changes in the landscape may reduce the attractiveness of a given area for tourists and cause problems for businesses in the sector of tourism. This, in general, translates into losses for the local economy.

On a macroeconomic scale, soil acidification may increase the risk of food crises. This can be particularly dangerous when a crisis occurs in multiple regions simultaneously [84,85]. The high losses of nutrients applied through mineral fertilisation on soils with low pH increase production costs [39] and do not guarantee the expected yields, which can lead to shortages of agricultural raw materials and an increase in their prices. The consequences of excessive soil acidification can also include disruptions in supply chains due to the phenomenon of the reduction in or disappearance of crops, which may ultimately prevent the farming or breeding of livestock. Additionally, excessive soil can result in a reduction in the number of jobs in the agricultural sector and agri-businesses. The decrease in the production scale or quality of agricultural products leads to a decrease in the raw material base.

The group of negative effects of soil acidification also includes increasing adaptation costs. To increase the productivity of agriculture on acidified soils, it is necessary to carry out costly and time-consuming technological investments and practices that allow farmers to constantly control and correct the soil's reaction to optimal production conditions. The effects of soil acidification include the costs of direct support for soil-liming treatments and the costs of educational campaigns highlighting good agricultural practices and the impact of fertilisation on water eutrophication and environmental quality. In this case, an essential role is played by institutional support, which, through the use of appropriate legal and financial instruments, influences the intensity of the use of lime fertilisers by farmers [39].

4. Conclusions

The implementation of the European Green Deal objectives is a serious challenge for agriculture not only in Poland but in the entire European community. Farmers, wishing to maintain their profitability levels, will have to optimise soil conditions and adapt techniques to meet the requirements of the EGD³. Without a cautious approach to the complexity of agrotechnical techniques and control of the soil pH, it will be extremely difficult to maintain current yield levels and produce quality crops, especially since a significant

portion of Polish land is dominated by acidic and very acidic soils. It should be expected that requirements of the EGD³ will promote a wider spread of soil liming.

As the survey results indicate, the (weak) institutional support and implementation of programs related to liming is insufficient to motivate all farmers to test their soils and incorporate liming treatments into soil cultivation in Poland. A significant number of farmers have not and are not liming their soils systematically. Such a situation in Poland, where the majority of agriculturally used soils are acidified, contributes to yield decreases and environmental degradation. Furthermore, liming applications are often too low to raise pH levels to appropriate values. The causes of this situation can be attributed to social, technological–logistical–technical, and economic factors. To change the existing situation, it is necessary to take effective steps to motivate farmers to lime their soils. The most effective steps include the following:

- Offering training courses for farmers to discuss the benefits that a farmer can achieve by maintaining optimum soil pH levels while growing a specific crop species;
- Implementing liming payment programs that will be more attractive and motivating from the farmers' perspective;
- Linking agri-environmental payments to the necessity of systematic testing of soil pH levels and maintaining optimal pH levels under specific crops species.

The authors hope that the analysis presented in this paper will lead to further analyses and discussions on this important issue.

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